

Procedure for semi-automatic parsing of Romance corpora

Table of Contents

Part I: Introduction	2
Part II: Suggested procedure	5
II.1. Digitisation.....	5
II.2. Automatic parsing.....	6
II.3. Correction of the automatic annotation	9
II.3.A. File upload.....	9
II.3.B. Manual correction.....	12
II.4. “Bootstrapping” your corpus	18
II.4.A. Training a base UD model	19
II.4.B. Preparing the first corpus to “finetune” the base model	20
II.4.C. “Finetuning” the base model	21
Part III. Sample Grew queries	23
Part IV. Resources and useful links	25

Part I: Introduction

NB: Links to tools and resources suggested are provided in Part III, below

For linguists, literary scholars, philologists, historians and researchers in other humanities disciplines, it may be useful to have grammatical information about texts written in different historical periods. For larger texts or corpora, this information takes a long time to produce manually but can be obtained by automatic annotation.

The goal of this document is to describe the stages that researchers can follow in order to syntactically annotate a text or a collection of texts in a Romance language of any period and correct the annotations.¹ No technical expertise is required to follow the steps described below, although users familiar with computational methods (e.g. Python programming language) can more easily adapt the procedure to their more specific needs, for example by installing and running the software on their machines, training models locally and manipulating files using dedicated Python libraries (tools and resources used are cited throughout the document, and the information is summarised in Section [IV. Resources and useful links](#)).

To add grammatical information to texts, we recommend using a technology called “syntactic parser”. The parser is a computer program that can use existing annotated data (the *training* corpus) in order to predict parts-of-speech (*tagging*) and syntactic functions (*parsing*) (and sometimes morphological features) of words in sentences of a new corpus that needs to be annotated (the *target* corpus). A parser thus has a double function: **Function 1**) it can use an annotated *training* corpus in a particular language to produce a resource for future syntactic analysis called a “model” (encoded information about the structure of the language); and **Function 2**) it can apply the pre-trained model to a new set of non-annotated data (*target* corpus) in order to automatically annotate it.

Some of the tools presented in this document allow using models pretrained on existing standard corpora (Function 2 of the parser) to annotate new *target* corpora. Others can be used to train models on existing and new annotated corpora (Function 1 of the parser). They also allow adapting, or “finetuning”, models by progressively adding some new annotated and corrected data.

A parser can therefore be used to convert a text into a collection of syntactic trees (Figure 1), known as a “treebank”. “Graph-based” syntactic parsers (e.g. UDPipe, BertForDeprel or HOPS)²

¹ We would also like to refer the reader to the document “How to Create a (UD) Treebank” on the Universal Dependencies website https://universaldependencies.org/contributing/how_to_start.html.

² UDPipe can be downloaded via <https://github.com/ufal/udpipe> (see also Straka M., Hajič J. and Straková J. (2016) UDPipe: Trainable Pipeline for Processing CoNLL-U Files Performing Tokenization, Morphological Analysis, POS Tagging and Parsing. In *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)*, European Language Resources Association (ELRA), Portorož, Slovenia, pp. 4290–4297). This parser is integrated into the UDPipe pipeline available at <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe>. BertForDeprel can be downloaded via <https://github.com/kiranguiller/BertForDeprel> (see also Guiller K. (2020). *Analyse syntaxique automatique du pidgin-créole du Nigeria à l'aide d'un transformer (BERT): Méthodes et Résultats*. (Master's dissertation, Sorbonne Nouvelle). This parser is integrated into ArboratorGrew (<https://arborator.grew.fr>). HOPS parser can be downloaded at <https://github.com/hopsparser/hopsparser> (Grobol, L. and Crabbé, B. (2021). Analyse en dépendances du français avec des plongements contextualisés. In *Actes de la 28ème Conférence sur le Traitement Automatique des Langues Naturelles, TALN-RÉCITAL 2021*, Lille, France, 10 pp. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-03223424>).

follow the architecture proposed by Dozat and Manning in 2017.³ For some languages, e.g. Old French and Old Italian, models and training corpora exist. Nevertheless, even with models trained on existing *training* corpora and applied to *target* corpora in the same language, the parser can produce annotations which may, however, be less satisfactory due to the genre of a text (not included in the initial data used to produce a model) and other factors (such as length of sentences), requiring manual corrections and model retraining. At the same time, for many languages, no models or training corpora are available. In this case, they can be created via adaptation of an existing model of a closely related language and an extensive programme of correction. In section [III.4 ‘Bootstrapping’ your corpus](#) of this document, we suggest a course of action for the adaptation of the parsing model to your language or your specific corpus, based on the “bootstrapping” methodology for syntactic parsing.⁴ It involves several rounds of correction of “pre-parsed” data and several rounds of retraining of the model via a user-friendly interface.

Please note that the parsers recommended use word embeddings (i.e., mathematical representations of words and their proximity encoded as vectors) and are then “finetuned” on corpus data; they are not rule-based. These tools provide predictions based on the context and, although they are very powerful, there will always be a margin of error. Occasionally, parsers will make mistakes and predict structures absent from the training corpus (e.g., two subjects depending from a single verb) or attribute to a token (i.e. word) a part-of-speech (PoS) tag that is inconsistent with the predicted syntactic function (e.g., tag a word as a pronoun with a determiner function). In addition to the errors resulting from the distance between the *training* corpus and the *target* corpus, it is about this type of errors that a researcher correcting an automatically annotated corpus should be particularly vigilant (see section [II.3.B Manual correction](#)).

The approach presented in this document is based on the use of the Universal Dependencies (UD) syntactic annotation framework, the framework most adapted for graph-based parsers.⁵ Most of the tasks are performed using ArboratorGrew software via the online portal. This tool is widely used by the international community of researchers, it provides a user-friendly platform for collaborative syntactic annotation of corpora, for training models and adapting them to new *target* data (“finetuning”), for automatic parsing, manual correction of automatic annotation and it can also be used for interrogation of annotated corpora.⁶

³ Dozat T.C. and Manning, C. D. (2017) Deep Biaffine Attention for Neural Dependency Parsing. *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*. 8 pp. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.01734>.

⁴ Peng Z., Gerdes K. and Guiller K. (2022) Pull your treebank up by its own bootstraps. In *Journées Jointes des Groupements de Recherche Linguistique Informatique, Formelle et de Terrain (LIFT) et Traitement Automatique des Langues (TAL)*, Marseille, pp.139-153. <https://hal.science/LISN-TLP/hal-03846834v1>.

⁵ De Marneffe, M.-C., Manning, C.D., Nivre, J. & Zeman, D. (2021). Universal Dependencies. In: *Computational Linguistics*, 47:2, pp. 255-308.

⁶ <https://arborator.grew.fr> (Guibon, G., Courtin, M. Gerdes, K. and Guillaume, B. (2020) When Collaborative Treebank Curation Meets Graph Grammars. In *Proceedings of The 12th Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, May 2020, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association, pp. 5293-5302. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.651>).

Figure 1. A sample syntactic tree from the CorAG corpus of Old Gascon (*Fors de Béarn*, 1560), annotated in Universal Dependencies and visualised with the ArboratorGrew software.⁷

The principles and guidelines of the Universal Dependencies annotation are described on the UD project website.⁸ Each sentence contains a number of tokens (or nodes) linked by syntactic relations. Each node has a parent node (governor, or head) and some nodes have children nodes (dependents). The head of the sentence is dependent on the artificial “root” node. The information about the trees is encoded in the CONLL-U format (Figure 2).⁹

```
# sent_id = 1460_Bearn_1_1_128_1_2
# len = 5
# text = Assi ditz la cort.
1      Assi      -      ADV      -      -      2      advmod  -      -
2      ditz      -      VERB     -      -      0      root    -      -
3      la       -      DET      -      -      4      det     -      -
4      cort     -      NOUN     -      -      2      nsubj   -      SpaceAfter=No
5      .        -      PUNCT    -      -      2      punct  -      -
```

Figure 2. Encoding the annotation of the tree presented in Figure 1 in the CONLL-U. The attribute len was added by the developers of the treebank to encode the length of the sentence.

A CONLL-U file contains information about the encoded sentences. For each sentence, the sentence ID attribute (number of the sentence in the treebank) and the text attribute (the sentence in plain text) need to be provided, followed by a table containing the list of tokens in the sentence. As a minimum, a CONLL-U file has to have the number of the tokens in the sentence (column 1, the artificial root node is not explicitly included), the form of the token (column 2), Universal part

⁷ The corpus is available at https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_Old_Occitan-CorAG and can be accessed via https://universal.grew.fr/?corpus=UD_Old_Occitan-CorAG@2.17.

⁸ <https://universaldependencies.org/guidelines.html>. A particularly useful introduction to the way syntactic functions are used in UD can be found at <https://universaldependencies.org/u/dep/all.html>.

⁹ Originally developed to be used during Conference On Natural Language Learning, CONLL, shared tasks and adopted by the Universal Dependencies project (<https://universaldependencies.org/format.html>).

of speech (upos) (column 4),¹⁰ the number of the governor node (column 7), the syntactic function (deprel) (column 8). In the example in Figures 1 and 2, the determiner (DET) “la” is the third token in the sentence, that is linked to its governor (noun “cort”, the fourth token in the sentence) by the syntactic relation det. This is the minimal information required for a valid CONLL-U file.¹¹ The lemma of the token can be added in column 2, a part of speech in a different framework (e.g. Penn framework¹²) can be supplied in column 5, morphological features of the token can be recorded in column 6 and column 9 is reserved for any extra information the creators of the treebank may want to add. For example, an attribute SpaceAfter=No may be added there to indicate that the token is not separated from the following token by a space (e.g. tokens before a punctuation mark).

Function 1 of the parser (training of models) allows learning from all the information contained in the CONLL-U file. Therefore, if the *training corpus* has been annotated in PoS and syntactic functions only, the model produced will be able to predict (Function 2 of the parser) only PoS and syntactic functions of the *target corpus*. If the *training corpus* has annotation in morphological features, the model will be able to predict those too.¹³

CONLL-U files (that will contain the number of the token in the sentence, the form of the token and the general structure of the file in ten columns) can be generated automatically from a plain text. It can then be annotated automatically and/or manually and corrected.

Part II: Suggested procedure

This procedure combines the use of several online tools and does not require technical expertise.

II.1. Digitisation

If the text you would like to analyse does not exist in a digitised format, you can use a platform for collaborative transcription such as TACTEO.¹⁴ Alternatively, you can use a tool for automatic character recognition (OCR) of printed text or handwritten text recognition (HTR) such as Transkribus (proprietary tool, available via a user-friendly online application at, 50 credits free every month)¹⁵ or eScriptorium (you need to contact the team and install the software on your machine).¹⁶ These tools allow digitising printed or handwritten texts automatically using

¹⁰ For a list of Universal PoS tags, see <https://universaldependencies.org/u/pos/index.html>.

¹¹ Some treebanks in the Universal Dependencies collection contain only this information, some also contain lemmatisation and morphological features. <https://universal.grew.fr/> page is a useful starting point for exploring existing UD corpora.

¹² See, for example Mitchell P. M., Santorini, B. and Marcinkiewicz M.A. (1993). Building a Large Annotated Corpus of English: The Penn Treebank. *Computational Linguistics*, 19:2, pp. 313–330.

¹³ On morphological features used in UD framework, see <https://universaldependencies.org/u/feat/index.html>.

¹⁴ <https://tacteo.huma-num.fr>. The platform is designed to facilitate collaborative transcription by several researchers. It also incorporates an instance of Tesseract software (<https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract>) that can be used for optical character recognition.

¹⁵ <https://www.transkribus.org>.

¹⁶ <https://escriptorium.rich.ru.nl>.

pretrained models and adapt models to your data if necessary. In any case, some measure of manual correction may be necessary.

The resulting transcription will need to be downloaded as plain text and saved in TXT format (e.g. file myCorpus.txt).

In order to produce analysed trees, the parser needs the text to be clearly segmented into minimal and maximal units of analysis, i.e., tokens and sentences. At the next stage, white spaces between words will be automatically used as limits of tokens (punctuation signs will be automatically treated as separate tokens) and strings of tokens between full stops as sentences.

Note that if you are digitising a manuscript text, additional editorial intervention may be required as you will need to make sure that it contains punctuation to enable automatic sentence segmentation.¹⁷

II.2. Automatic parsing

- a) Open UDPipe portal at <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/run.php>.

This is a website integrating an automatic parser¹⁸ and a set of models trained on corpora from the UD collection. The selection of models is determined by the availability of training corpora in the collection.¹⁹ For some languages, several corpora and thus several models are available and you may want to find out about the contents of the corpus or test the model on a small sample of your data before deciding which model will be more appropriate for your work.

The <https://universal.grew.fr> website gives access to UD corpora. The corpora can be sorted by language. For example, for French, nine corpora are currently available. In addition to standard written modern French corpora (e.g. GSD²⁰ and Sequoia²¹), the collection has, for example, two spoken corpora (Rhapsodie²² and ParisStories²³), a corpus of poitevin-saintongeais - a regional language of the *oil* group (PoitevinDIVITAL²⁴), a corpus of sixteenth-century legal texts from Normandy and the Channel Islands (ALTS²⁵). To identify the corpus with the language closest to the data you would like to annotate, the easiest way is to go to <https://universal.grew.fr/>, select a on which the model is based from the left-hand menu and click on the GitHub logo (Figure 3). This will redirect you to the repository of the corpus containing the source CONLL-U files and the

¹⁷ ArboratorGrew documentation provides information on how to edit token and sentence segmentation once your file has been uploaded (<https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/annotation>, sections “Sentence segmentation” and “Token editing options”).

¹⁸ Straka M., Hajič J. and Straková J. (2016) UDPipe: Trainable Pipeline for Processing CoNLL-U Files Performing Tokenization, Morphological Analysis, POS Tagging and Parsing. In *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'16)*, European Language Resources Association (ELRA), Portorož, Slovenia. pp. 4290–4297.

¹⁹ At the time of writing, models available via the UDPipe portal correspond to the 2.15 release of the UD collection, November 2024.

²⁰ https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-GSD.

²¹ https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-Sequoia.

²² https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-Rhapsodie.

²³ At the time of writing, models available via the UDPipe portal correspond to the 2.15 release of the UD collection, November 2024.

https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-ParisStories.

²⁴ https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-PoitevinDIVITAL.

²⁵ https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-ALTS.

description of the data, including the size of the corpus, the texts that are included, dates and genre (see also section [II.4.A. Training a base UD model](#)).

Figure 3. GitHub logo on the GrewMatch page of the UD_Italian-Old corpus.

Back on the UDPipe portal, from the drop-down menu, select the model of a language trained on a UD corpus closest to your *target corpus* (your file *myCorpus.txt*). E.g., if you are working on Old Catalan you may want to try using a model for modern Catalan.

- b) Upload the file *myCorpus.txt* into the “Input file” tab (Figure 4).
- c) Press “Process Input”.

A CONLL-U file will be automatically generated from the TXT file (the text will be broken down into tokens and sentences and a table created for each sentence). This initial CONLL-U file will be annotated using the selected model. PoS tags and syntactic functions labels will be added to each token and dependency relationships between tokens, predicted by the model, will be added in the file. Depending on the model (and thus the *training corpus*), syntactic features may also be added (see Figures 5-6).

Figure 4: Model selection and file upload on the UDPipe portal.

Figure 5. Visualisation of the tree of a sentence from *Ponthus et Sidoine*, a medieval French romance (late 14th-early 15th century), parsed with a model for Old French on UDPipe portal.

d) You can now download the annotated file by pressing “Save Output File”.

The file will be saved in your Downloads folder. You can move it to another location and change the name of the file, for example to myCorpus.conllu, making sure to maintain the .conllu extension.


```
# generator = UDPipe 2, https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe
# udpipe_model = old_french-proffiterole-ud-2.15-241121
# udpipe_model_licence = CC BY-NC-SA
# newdoc
# newpar
# sent_id = 1
# text = et puis se mist en la forest de Breceilien en une prieuré
1 et _ CCONJ CONcoo _ 4 cc:nc _ TokenRange=0:2
2 puis _ ADV ADVgen _ 4 advmod _ TokenRange=3:7
3 se _ PRON PROper PronType=Prs 4 obj _ TokenRange=8:10
4 mist _ VERB VERcjk VerbForm=Fin 0 root _ TokenRange=11:15
5 en _ ADP PRE _ 7 case _ TokenRange=16:18
6 la _ DET DETdef Definite=DefPronType=Art 7 det _ TokenRange=19:21
7 forest _ NOUN NOMcom _ 4 obl _ TokenRange=22:28
8 de _ ADP PRE _ 9 case _ TokenRange=29:31
9 Breceilien _ PROPN NOMpro _ 7 nmod _ TokenRange=32:41
10 en _ ADP PRE _ 12 case _ TokenRange=42:44
11 une _ DET DETndf Definite=IndjPronType=Art 12 det _ TokenRange=45:48
12 prieuré _ NOUN NOMcom _ 4 obl _ SpaceAfter=No|TokenRange=49:56
```

Figure 6. CONLL-U of the sentence from Figure 5. Note the UD morphological features annotated (e.g. PronType=Prs, VerbForm=Fin). Column 5 contains annotation in CATTEX 2009,²⁶ present in the training corpus.

II.3. Correction of the automatic annotation

The rest of the work will be performed on the ArboratorGrew portal. The platform does not have a set of pre-trained standard models the way UDPipe does,²⁷ therefore we recommend starting the work on the latter (section [II.2. Automatic parsing](#)).

The following sections will guide you through the phases of the annotation and correction process but we also refer you to the ArboratorGrew documentation.²⁸

II.3.A. File upload

a) Go to the ArboratorGrew portal <https://arborator.grew.fr> and log in.

²⁶ See <http://bfm.ens-lyon.fr/spip.php?article176>.

²⁷ A page for parsing with pretrained models for French and Occitan is currently under development and the link will appear on the ArboratorGrew main page in due course.

²⁸ <https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/>.

In order to log in you will need a gmail ([gmail.com](mailto:)) or a GitHub (github.com) account.²⁹ When you press the “LOGIN” button in the upper right corner of the screen, you will be prompted to connect with your gmail or GitHub credentials.

b) Create a project for your corpus.

In order to start working on your myCorpus.conllu file annotated automatically, you need to create a project by pressing on the “New Project” button.

You will need to:

- provide the name of the project
- define its language (if the language of your text is not present in the list, you will give the name of the language closest to it or the language of the model you used to automatically parse your text)³⁰
- decide whether it will be public (i.e., visible to all users) or private; in the latter case you may need to share it with your collaborators so that they, too, have access to the data. In order to do so, you will need to go to “Settings”, then choose “Share”. You can share the project using a person’s Google email or GitHub username.

d) Upload the file you downloaded from UDPipe onto your project on ArboratorGrew.

In order to do so, you will click on the “New Sample” button and upload the automatically annotated file you downloaded from UDPipe (Figure 7).

²⁹ You may want to create a dedicated email account to use on ArboratorGrew.

³⁰ This functionality is currently under revision on ArboratorGrew. Specifying the language of your corpus allows validating your corpus, once it is annotated, with the language-specific guidelines defined by the UD community. If you cannot find your language in the list, you can also just type the name of the language in the field provided and press enter. The validation will, however, only be possible if specific language guidelines have been published (to check the languages currently on the collection, see the <https://universaldependencies.org/> page).

Figure 8. The button in a red square will save the tree you are working on as “validated”. The “disquette” button in a blue circle will save the tree under your username. The tree comes from UD_Old_French-ALTM corpus.³¹

Now your automatically parsed corpus is uploaded on ArboratorGrew and is ready to be visualised, interrogated and corrected.

II.3.B. Manual correction

At this stage, you may choose (1) to start using the automatic annotation you have just produced despite possible errors, or (2) to manually correct the whole file or (3) to correct a selection of sentences (e.g. 100-300 sentences) before training a new model to improve the quality of the automatic annotation. Much will depend on the quality of the automatic annotation produced earlier (section [II.2 Automatic parsing](#)). If the first model used was not very well adapted to your corpus (e.g. you used a model for modern Spanish to parse an Old Spanish text), there is a clear advantage to retraining your model several times with samples of corrected data to achieve better performance (see [III. Bootstrapping your corpus](#)).

If you are reasonably confident that the automatic annotation has yielded acceptable results (e.g. if you have parsed a modern French text with a model for modern French), you can consider this quality of annotation sufficient and start exploring your corpus. You can begin by using pre-formulated queries in the Grew tab on the ArboratorGrew platform (Figure 9).³² (See also [Part III. Sample Grew queries](#)).

³¹ The corpus is available at https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_Old_French-ALTM and can be consulted via https://universal.grew.fr/?corpus=UD_Old_French-ALTM@2.17.

³² The Grew query language tutorial gives a useful introduction to querying corpora annotated in Universal dependencies, it can be found by following the link to the Tutorial from the GrewMatch webpage: <https://match.grew.fr/>.

Figure 9. Explore your corpus using Grew queries. You will find some sample queries when you click on different options on the left-hand menu.

If you need to be sure of the reliability of the annotation of your corpus but you do not have time and resources to correct the whole text, you may want to conduct an evaluation of the annotation. This cannot currently be done without using Universal Dependencies evaluation scripts³³ and beginner programming skills will be required.

In order to set up an evaluation, you will need to correct at least a hundred sentences of your corpus (create what is called a “Gold” corpus, i.e., the reference corpus of “perfect”, or “Gold standard” annotation for evaluation purposes). Then, using the scripts, compare the corrected “Gold” version of the annotation to the annotation automatically produced by the parser. The standard measure used is Labelled Attachment Score (LAS) that gives a score from 0 to 1 (or a percentage) of the accuracy of the function labels and the attribution of syntactic heads.

Manual correction of annotation is a time-consuming task. For the functionalities of annotation and correction on ArboratorGrew, we refer you to the site documentation.³⁴ The most reliable approach to annotation is getting several experts to independently correct the annotation of each sentence and then to resolve any conflicts or issues arising. If time and resources are not available, we recommend supplementing manual verification with three types of controls: A) queries to identify structural inconsistencies of the trees; B) using the ArboratorGrew Lexicon function to control PoS attribution; 3) using ArboratorGrew Relation Table function to correct inconsistencies in the annotation of PoS and syntactic functions.

³³ Available via <https://universaldependencies.org/conll18/evaluation.html>.

³⁴ <https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/annotation>.

We also refer you to the ArboratorGrew documentation describing Grew search, Lexicon and Relation Table options.³⁵

A) Queries to identify structural inconsistencies of the trees

In this section, you will use Grew option of the ArboratorGrew portal (Figure 9) to run queries that will identify sentences with structural errors that may have been accidentally produced during automatic annotation. We also recommend using these queries at the end of the process of manual correction of the data to check for any accidental mistakes.

Table 1 presents a set of queries to identify structural errors in automatically or manually annotated trees. You will need to copy the query into the Search field of the Grew tab in your ArboratorGrew project, run the query and manually correct the mistakes.

Description	Query
<p>Identifies cyclical trees.</p> <p>The structure of a UD tree can be seen as a knowledge graph made of nodes that represent tokens (words and punctuation marks) and of arcs, symbolising syntactic relations. In this framework, every token can have a single head and can have one or more dependents. In this structure, a child node cannot have a dependent positioned higher up in the hierarchy of the tree as this would create a loop (a cycle).</p>	<code>global { is_cyclic }</code>
<p>Identifies incomplete trees.</p> <p>Sentences that have tokens that do not have a head and do not have a single token linked to the artificial “root” node numbered 0 (the entry into the graph).</p>	<code>global { is_not_tree }</code>
<p>Identifies non-projective structures.</p> <p>Non-projective structures are structures where dependency arcs are crossed. In UD, punctuation is the only function that cannot enter non-projective structures. Some languages will allow projective structures (e.g. a French example in Figure 10), therefore this query should be used with care.</p>	<code>global { is_not_projective }</code>
<p>Trees without a root.</p> <p>This query allows identifying trees without a root function that marks the head of the main clause.</p>	<code>without { X -[root]-> Y; X.__id__ = 0 }</code>

³⁵ <https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/advancedAnnotation>.

Tokens without a governor, or head.	pattern { X[form <> "__0__"] } without { Y -> X }
Identifies tokens without a PoS tag.	pattern { X[!upos, form <> "__0__"] }
Tokens without syntactic function label (deprel)	pattern { e: X -> Y; e.label = "_" }
Predicates with more than one subject In the UD framework, a predicate can have only one subject. All coordinated subjects should be attached to the first subject with the conj function. This error can be produced by automatic annotation or result from oversight during manual annotation.	X -[nsubj]-> Y; X -[nsubj]-> Z
Double objects The same rule applies to objects.	pattern { X -[obj]-> Y; X -[obj]-> Z }

Table 1. Grew queries to identify errors in syntactic trees.

C'est ce que nous devons éviter à tout prix.

Figure 10. Example of a non-projective structure from Sequoia corpus.³⁶

B) ArboratorGrew Lexicon function to control PoS attribution

Lexicon function on ArboratorGrew allows sorting tokens in your corpus according to the values annotated in the CONLL-U file. You can sort the tokens by upos (Universal PoS), form, any morphological features annotated and lemmata (if annotated). To facilitate correction of PoS annotation, we recommend producing a table that sorts the tokens by PoS and form. In order to do so, you will need to go to the Lexicon tab in your project's main menu, select "upos" from the "Similar features" drop-down menu and "form" from the "Ambiguous features" menu. If you have several files in your project, you will need to indicate the file(s) you want to work on in the "Select

³⁶ The corpus is available at https://github.com/UniversalDependencies/UD_French-Sequoia and can be consulted via https://universal.grew.fr/?corpus=UD_French-Sequoia@2.17.

sample” box (otherwise, all files will be included), and if you have several versions of the trees (e.g. the initial trees produced by automatic parsing, “validated” or trees saved under the individual annotators’ usernames) you will need to indicate which trees you need in the last box available (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Lexicon function on ArboratorGrew.

You will click on “Generate Lexicon” button and a table will appear that you can sort by PoS by clicking on the “Upos” label at the top of the first column. You can then check if the PoS tags have been correctly attributed to the forms in the second column. The number of sentences for each Upos=form combination appears in the third column. You can click on this number to navigate to the sentences and correct the occurrences if needed. If you click on the line containing the Upos=form combination, a pop-up window will open that will allow you to select the correct PoS tag for your form and save it for all sentences (NB the trees will be saved under your username) (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Pop-up window allowing to change the tag for all incorrectly annotated forms.

C) ArboratorGrew Relation Table function to correct inconsistencies in the annotation of PoS and syntactic functions

Relation table option on ArboratorGrew generates a set of tables for each syntactic function (deprel) annotated in the corpus. The PoS of the head of the function is indicated on the vertical axis of the table and the PoS of the dependent (i.e., the token annotated with the deprel) on the

horizontal axis. In order to generate the table, you will need to go to the “Relation table” tab in your project’s main menu. If you have several files in your project, you will need to indicate the file(s) you want to work on in the “Select sample” box (otherwise all files will be included) and if you have several versions of the trees (e.g. the initial trees produced by automatic parsing, “validated” or trees saved under the individual annotators’ usernames) you will need to indicate which trees you need in the last box available. Once the setup is finished, you can access the tables by pressing the “Generate relations table” button (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Generating Relations tables for all functions in the corpus.

All syntactic relations annotated in the files selected will be displayed in the column on the left. If some arcs have not been attributed a deprel label, a “-” sign will appear at the beginning of the list. Some syntactic functions, such as auxiliaries and copulas (aux and cop) and determiners (det) can have only one PoS option for, auxiliary (AUX) and determiner (DET) respectively. For others the options will be wider but still potentially limited. For example, you would not normally expect the head of the main clause to be a determiner (DET) or an adjectival modifier (amod) to be a noun (NOUN). We would therefore recommend using the Relations table to check for this type of anomalies after automatic annotation and then again after manual correction to eliminate any accidental errors that may have been introduced.

Another useful strategy is to check for exceptional combinations that occur once or twice in a corpus (see Figure 14).

Relation Table for "iobj" containing a total of 286 occurrences

	↓ Σ	PRON	NUM
Σ	286	285	1
VERB	285	284	1
ADV	1	1	

Figure 14. Relation table with exceptional combinations of governor and dependent PoS.

By clicking on the number of occurrences of each combination of governor and dependent PoS, you will be taken to the list of sentences containing the relevant combination. From this list, you can open each sentence (the arcs in question will be highlighted in red) and, if needed, correct the annotation.

II.4. “Bootstrapping” your corpus

If you find that the quality of the annotation achieved by following the steps described in section [II.2. Automatic parsing](#) is not sufficient for your work and it would be too time consuming to correct the whole corpus manually using this version, you may want to progressively adapt the parsing model to your corpus.³⁷ In order to do so, you will need to use the Parser option available on the ArboratorGrew website that integrates BertForDeprel parser.³⁸ No standard pretrained models are available on ArboratorGrew³⁹ but users can train their own models using annotated CONLL-U files (please note that only owners of a project, i.e. the person who created it, or users with administrator status can do so; administrator status can be conferred to collaborators by the owner of the project).⁴⁰

The methodology consists in training a model based on an existing UD corpus and correcting a small amount of your *target* corpus parsed with this model, then “finetuning” the model with your corrected (“Gold”) sentences before correcting another portion of your corpus analysed with the latest version of the model. The new corrected material will be used to progressively further adapt the model. For example, if you are working with an Old Catalan text, you may want to train a model on a modern Catalan corpus, then “finetune” the model with some corrected Old Catalan sentences and continue the process through several rounds of adaptation.

Our recent experiments with annotating Old Gascon have shown that, in the absence (at the time of start of work) of an appropriate model (or *training* corpus) for any dialect of Old Occitan, “finetuning” a model based on a Romance corpus (Old French, Old Italian or Modern Occitan) on only a hundred sentences of different lengths can raise the performance of the model from 50-55% to 75% and “finetuning” with 600 sentences achieves 85% accuracy rate.⁴¹ In another study, we have shown that parser performance decreases on longer sentences (this no doubt due to the architecture of the parser⁴²) and, therefore, using longer sentences or at least a mixture of longer

³⁷ This approach is inspired by Peng et al (2021).

³⁸ Giller (2020). A short introduction to the functionality is available in the ArboratorGrew documentation (<https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/parser>).

³⁹ See note 27.

⁴⁰ For more information on project configuration on ArboratorGrew, we refer you to the guidelines <https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/projectConfig>.

⁴¹ Romanova, N., Ziane, R. & Francioni, B., (2025). Adaptation of models for parsing of Old Gascon. In *Proceedings of Journées scientifiques du réseau thématique LIFT2 linguistique informatique, formelle et de terrain*. 16-17 October 2025, Paris. (8pp.) <https://lift2-2025.sciencesconf.org/667164>

⁴² Daoudi, K., Dehouck, M., Romanova, N. & Ziane, R., (2025). Explicit Edge Length Coding to Improve Long Sentence Parsing Performance. In *Proceedings of the First Workshops on Advancing NLP for Low-Resource Languages*. 13 September 2025, Varna, Bulgaria. (pp. 102-110). URL: <https://acl-bg.org/proceedings/2025/LowResNLP%202025/index.html>.

and shorter sentences for the initial rounds of “finetuning” may be beneficial if your corpus contains sentences longer than 30 tokens.⁴³

Please note that you may choose to start training a model directly with your own corrected data but, in our experience, having a base model yields much better results much quicker (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Bootstrapping a model for Old Gascon
(base corpora: OI - Old Italian, PRFT - Old French, TTB - modern Occitan).⁴⁴

In what follows, therefore, we will describe a process based on training a base model for parsing of your corpus and progressively adapting it to your data.

II.4.A. Training a base UD model

This first “base” model can serve to parse your text for the first time before correcting a hundred sentences that will be used to “finetune” the model to start adapting it to your data. Alternatively, you can correct the first sentences manually or start with the automatic annotation produced by a model on the UDPipe portal (Section [II. Automatic parsing](#)). In any case, the base model is an important part of the suggested process.

To begin with, you will need to choose the UD treebank on which your base model will be trained. If no treebank exists for the language, language variety, historical period or genre of your corpus, it may make sense to choose a UD corpus in a language variety that is the closest.⁴⁵ You can use the <https://universal.grew.fr> website to explore corpora that are available in the current release of the UD collection and then navigate to the GitHub repository of the selected corpus by pressing

⁴³ Ziane, R. & Romanova, N. (2024). Pistes pour l’optimisation des modèles de parsing syntaxique. *Proceedings of LIFT 2-2024, Orléans* (7 pp.). <https://lift2-2024.sciencesconf.org/590561/document>.

⁴⁴ See Romanova et al 2025, p. 4.

⁴⁵ As shown in Figure 15, linguistic closeness, at least where languages of the same group are concerned, may be of limited importance if subsequent retraining is envisaged as we had very similar results with three Romance corpora, we used to train models to annotate Old Gascon (Romanova et al 2025, p. 4). When selecting the corpus, you may also take into account the genre of the texts in the corpus, sentence length and annotation choices made by the project team to make sure that they correspond best to your approach.

the GitHub logo button (Figure 3). On the GitHub page, you can read information about the corpus and download the CONLL-U files. UD corpora repositories contain three files - train, dev and test,⁴⁶ - and you may find it useful to download all three to have more training data.

You will then need to create an ArboratorGrew project, give it a name that will help you identify the model you will create, and upload the CONLL-U files of your selected corpus. Then you will need to go to the “Parser” tab on the main project menu and click the “Train new model” button (Figure 16). A new screen will open and you will need to select the “Train only” option (Figure 17) and click on the “Start” button at the bottom of the page. Training of the model will start. It can take some time, depending on the size of the training data and on the availability of the server. Once training is finished, a message will be displayed on your screen.

Figure 16: Parser screen.

Figure 17. Training the first model.

II.4.B. Preparing the first corpus to “finetune” the base model

If you are starting with a TXT file, you may want to use UDPipe portal to convert your TXT file into CONLL-U and parse it with a model available there and then download the result (see section [II.2 Automatic parsing](#)). This is the easiest user-friendly way to obtain a CONLL-U file (currently, only CONLL-U files can be uploaded). Otherwise, you can paste it directly into the “Input Text”

⁴⁶ i.e., the data is prepared for the evaluation of models that may be trained on this corpus by different parsing technologies. Yet this evaluation will only be valid for the language of the corpus and performances will vary when the model is applied to other types of data. We therefore suggest you use all of the data available when you train your first model on ArboratorGrew. Treebanks smaller than 20,000 tokens will only have one test file (for more information on UD guidelines for data split, see the “Data split” section on the “Repository and files” page of the UD documentation (https://universaldependencies.org/contributing/repository_files.html)).

field in the pop-up window opening when you click on the “New Sample” button and ArboratorGrew will convert it into a CONLL-U file.

You can then parse the data with the new model you trained in section [II.4.A. Training a base UD model](#). You can parse the version you downloaded from UDPipe, and the parser will create a new tree and save the initial version. In order to do so, you need to go into the “Parser” tab on the menu. The list of models trained on the portal will appear. You will need to select the model you have just trained (it will have the name of the folder in which you uploaded your selected UD corpus) and click on “Parse Samples”. The new trees that will be annotated automatically with the base model will be given the name “parser” but you can give it an extension (a “suffix”), for example add the name of the model and/or the date of parsing (Figure 18). Once you press the “Start” button, the parsing will take a few minutes, and the trees will appear alongside the first set of uploaded trees in the “Samples” tab. If you uploaded a CONLL-U file parsed on UDPipe, you can parse it with the new model and you will have two versions of automatic parsing (one by UDPipe, one by BertForDeprel integrated to ArboratorGrew) to choose from when you start corrections.

Figure 18. Adding a suffix to the name of the automatically annotated trees.

At this stage, we recommend correcting 100 sentences from your data. You can do this manually by rereading the sentences and integrating controls described in section [II.3.B. Manual correction](#). You may want to correct the sentences in the order of the text or choose longer sentences or a selection of sentences of different lengths. When you open your sample, a menu on the top allows you to sort the sentences in order of appearance in the text (“Initial”), from the shortest to the longest (“Ascending”) or from the longest to the shortest (“Descending”). Once you are happy with the annotation, you can click on the “validation” button (Figure 3) to create a validated version of the tree you will be using to “finetune” your base model.

II.4.C. “Finetuning” the base model

Once you have a set of validated sentences, you can start “finetuning” your base model to better adapt it to your data and get better annotation at the next round of parsing and thus spend less time correcting it. In order to do so, you will stay in the folder where your corpus containing a set of corrected and validated sentences is. You will go to the “Parser” tab, indicate that you want to “Train only” and choose your base model (the model you created in section [III.4.A Training a base UD model](#)), then make sure that you indicate that you need to retrain your model on the validated trees from your project only (Figure 19).

Once the model is trained, you can parse the sample again, making sure that you indicate the name of the trees you want to parse (the trees that were created after the upload of plain text or the CONLL-U downloaded from UDPipe) and the suffix for the new trees annotated with the new model (Figure 18). You can then proceed to correcting another batch of data, that will then be used for “finetuning” of a new model. This process means that you will parse all trees several times, but you will only correct the trees that have not yet got a “validated” version. Once all of your text has been validated, you have the “Gold” version of your corpus. You can delete all the other versions and start exploring the validated version using Grew queries.

Figure 19. Indicating the name of the trees to be used for retraining.

Part III. Sample Grew queries

Syntactic structures in corpora annotated in Universal Dependencies can be identified using Grew query language. In the table below, we provide sample queries in Grew query language that may be relevant for exploring corpora in Romance languages. Please note that the names of the variables (here e.g., X, Y, Z) are not meaningful and can be changed (e.g., you may want to call your “subject” variable “S” etc.).

We recommend using Grew language tutorial to familiarise yourself with the syntax of the language and gain confidence to formulate your own queries.⁴⁷ The same queries can be used on the corpora in the UD collection available via <https://universal.grew.fr>.

Description	Query
Nouns with determiners	pattern { X -[det]-> Y; X[upos=NOUN] }
Nouns without determiners	pattern { X[upos=NOUN] } without { X -[det]-> Y }
Nouns with determiners and adjectival modifiers	pattern { X -[det]->Z; X -[amod]-> Y; X[upos=NOUN] }
Nouns with adjectival modifiers without determiners	pattern { X -[amod]-> Y; X[upos=NOUN] } without { X -[det]->Z }
Root clauses without a subject	pattern { X -[root]-> Y } without { Y -[nsubj]->S }
Completive clauses without a subject	pattern { X -[ccomp]-> Y } without { Y -[nsubj]->S }
Completive clauses with a nominal subject	pattern { X -[ccomp]-> Y; Y -[nsubj]->S; S[upos=NOUN] }
Completive clauses with a nominal subject positioned after the head of the clause	pattern { X -[ccomp]-> Y; Y -[nsubj]->S; S[upos=NOUN]; Y<<S }

Table 2: Sample Grew queries to explore UD annotated corpora.

⁴⁷ Follow the link from the GrewMatch webpage: <https://match.grew.fr>.

Je voudrais bien savoir à quoi rime tout leur verbiage ?

Figure 20: Example of a query “Completive clause with a nominal subject positioned after the head of the clause” from the Sequoia corpus (visualisation https://universal.grew.fr/?corpus=UD_French-Sequoia@2.17).

For example, in Figure 20, there is an example of an occurrence that was returned when using a query targeting “Completive clauses with a nominal subject positioned after the head of the clause” in the UD2.17 version of the Sequoia corpus (modern French). The following Grew query was used:

```
pattern { X -[ccomp]-> Y;
         Y-[nsubj]->S;
         S[upos=NOUN];
         Y<<S }
```

Firstly, we have three variables, X, Y and S. Then, the syntactic relation between X and Y is defined: Y is the head of the completive clause (ccomp) dependent on X. Another syntactic relation, this time between Y and S, is declared: S is the subject (nsubj) of Y. Therefore, we have a completive clause that has a subject. The PoS of the subject is then defined: only completive clauses with a subject that is a noun (NOUN) will be requested. A final condition is imposed on the requested structure: the subject (S) follows the head of the completive clause (Y), This condition is expressed with two left angle brackets (chevrons). Two angle brackets mean that S is positioned to the right of Y, but it can either immediately follow the latter or be separated from it by one or more tokens. A single angle bracket (<) would require S to immediately follow Y.

Part IV. Resources and useful links

Resource	Description	Link
I. General		
Syntactic framework	Universal Dependencies (UD)	https://universaldependencies.org/
CONLL-U	File format used in UD	https://universaldependencies.org/format.html
UD syntactic framework annotation guidelines	General (UD) annotation guidelines (follow links for language-specific guidelines)	https://universaldependencies.org/guidelines.html
UD treebank collection on GitHub	UD GitHub pages containing descriptions of treebanks and the annotated data in CONLL-U format	https://github.com/universalddependencies
GrewMatch UD	UD treebanks available for querying using Grew query language	https://universal.grew.fr/
Grew	Graph-rewriting tool for NLP (used in ArboratorGrew and other UD-based tools)	https://grew.fr/
Grew-match tutorial	Introduction to queries and commands when using Grew tools	https://team.inria.fr/semagramme/files/2021/02/Grew-match-tuto.pdf
II. Parsers, models and parsing platforms		
ArboratorGrew	Collaborative treebank annotation and parsing tool, available online and for	Online portal

	installation	https://arborator.grew.fr Code https://github.com/Arborator Documentation https://arborator.github.io/arborator-documentation/#/
BertForDeprel	Graph-based parser (requires installation) This parser is integrated into ArboratorGrew with XLM Roberta Large embeddings	https://github.com/kirianguiller/BertForDeprel
XLM Roberta Model	Facebook AI XLM Roberta Large Model (a transformers model pretrained on a large corpus in a self-supervised fashion)	https://huggingface.co/FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-large
HOPS	Graph-based parser with pretrained models (requires installation)	https://github.com/hopsparser/hopsparser
HOPS pretrained models	Pre-trained models for French and Medieval French to be used with HOPS parser	https://hopsparser.readthedocs.io/en/latest/models.html
ArboratorGrew Parser	Online parsing with a selection of parsing models trained on UD corpora (under construction)	https://parser.grew.fr
UDPipe	UDPipe pipeline for tokenisation and parsing using models pretrained on UD-Treebanks	https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/udpipe/run.php Code https://github.com/ufal/udpipe

III. Scripts		
UD evaluation scripts	The scripts that allow evaluating the performance of the model on your data (requires a “gold” corpus)	https://universaldependencies.org/conll18/evaluation.html
Grewpy Python library	A Python library that allows to query conllu files	https://github.com/grew-nlp/grewpy
Grewpy Python library tutorial	An introduction to Grewpy	https://grew.fr/grewpy/tutorial
CRISCO-HT pipeline	Pipeline for annotation of French texts from txt that produces XML and CONLL files as output Contains sample Python scripts for converting txt files into XML and CONLL	https://github.com/Corpus-Diachroniques-CRISCO/HT-CRISCO
GreX tool	Tool for automatic grammar extraction from annotated treebanks Requires installation on your computer and Python skills	https://github.com/FilippoC/grex-lrec-coling-2024
IV. Transcription, OCR and HTR tools		
Transkribus	Online tool for automatic handwritten text recognition (HTR) and optical character recognition of digitised sources, provides pre-trained models and options to train data (limited use free, requires paid subscription afterwards)	https://www.transkribus.org/ Online tutorials https://www.youtube.com/@transkribus

eScriptorium	Tool for automatic handwritten text recognition (HTR) and optical character recognition of digitised sources, provides pre-trained models and options to train data	https://msia.escriptorium.fr/ Documentation https://escriptorium.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
TACT software and Tacteo platform for collaborative transcription	Platform for collaborative transcription of manuscript	Online platform https://tacteo.huma-num.fr/ Code for installation https://gricad-gitlab.univ-grenoble-alpes.fr/elan/tact
Tesseract	OCR software	https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract